

LEGAL PRINCIPLES OF BUILDING A DEMOCRATIC SOCIETY.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6642565>

Dadaev Bokhodir Gayrat o'g'li

*Student of the Faculty of International Law,
University of World Economy and Diplomacy*

Annotation: The content of the article concerns the legal principles necessary for building a democratic society and the democracy that is considered important today, which can be built on the basis of these principles. This article discusses the role and importance of democracy in the development of society on the basis of a system analysis, taking into account a number of theoretical considerations.

Keywords: democratic society, legal principles, democracy, opinion, system analysis.

Introduction: Uzbekistan is a sovereign democratic republic.¹ Today the world has developed certain moderate scientific ideas about democracy, a democratic society. They more and more reflect the image, foundations and universally recognized laws of the development of a democratic society, as well as its aspects related to the national and spiritual characteristics of each state and people.²

The democratic society under construction in the Republic of Uzbekistan is connected with this law - the need to identify and study its specific features.

The principles of democracy are complemented by national values. It is also necessary to study and analyze this process in our society, the socio-political events that take place around us and the interrelationships between them with our realities. The importance of this can be seen in the words of the first President I.A. Karimov: "Our ultimate goal is to build a strong democratic state governed by the rule of law

¹ www.lex.uz Article 1 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

² Azizxo'jaev A.A Democracy means people's power. – T.: 1996.

and a civil society with a socially oriented stable market economy and an open foreign policy".³

The task of building a democratic society in Uzbekistan is in line with the principles of civil society, aimed at ensuring human rights and freedoms, their equality before the law. Knowing the conditions and main directions for achieving it gives a holistic view of a democratic society. These are some unhealthy behaviors that contradict democracy in our lives today, "under the guise of democracy" its national and spiritual features, the way of life of the people of Uzbekistan, national and spiritual values: history, language, helps to understand the essence of the original purpose of the unilateral, impartial attempts to assess democracy, regardless of culture, customs and traditions.

Democracy is a system of government in which power and civic responsibility are exercised by all citizens directly or through their freely elected representatives;

Democracy is based on the principles of majority rule and private law. A democratic state does not allow the central government to increase its power, ensures that all levels of government are open to citizens, and decentralizes regional and local governments so that they can reflect the needs of all people;

³ I.A.Karimov. O'zbekiston XXI asr bo'sag'asida: xavfsizlikka tahdid, barqarorlik shartlari va taraqqiyot kafolatlari T: O'zbekiston, 1997, page 3.

Conclusions: We have set ourselves the glorious goal of building a new Uzbekistan together with our people. In this regard, the new idea of "Society - the initiator of reforms" is becoming more and more deeply ingrained in our daily work.⁴

We still have a long way to go to improve the quality of governance by fully implementing the basic principle, "The people should not serve the public authorities, but the public authorities should serve the people".⁵

The work done in recent years to implement democratic reforms in our country, including the promotion of human rights and freedoms and the rule of law, is proof of the above considerations.

At the same time, the tasks ahead of us are much more serious and far-reaching than our efforts to protect and ensure human rights and freedoms.

References:

1. www.lex.uz Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan.
2. I.A.Karimov. O'zbekiston XXI asr bo'sag'asida: xavfsizlikka tahdid, barqarorlik shartlari va taraqqiyot kafolatlari T: Uzbekistan, 1997, page 3.
3. <https://review.uz/uz/post/uzbekiston-respublikasi-prezidenti-savkat-mirzиеevning-olij-mazlisga-murozaatnomasi> Petition of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis. 28.01.2020.
4. Azizxo'jaev A.A Democracy means people's power. – T.: 1996.

⁴ <https://review.uz/uz/post/uzbekiston-respublikasi-prezidenti-savkat-mirzиеevning-olij-mazlisga-murozaatnomasi> Petition of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis. 28.01.2020.

⁵ Petition of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis. 28.01.2020.